

Profile of Paediatric Morbidity in Hospitals in the Democratic Republic of the Congo from 2019 to 2021

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Abstract

Knowledge of morbidity is essential for planning and evaluating health services and assessing a country's level of social and economic development. At a global level, morbidity is constantly evolving in line with the

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epidemiological transition. This study aims to describe the profile of paediatric hospital morbidity in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC).

It is a retrospective, multicentre, cross-sectional study conducted between 2019 and 2021 in five referral health facilities in four cities of the country.

Of the 2,170 cases analysed, 70% of admissions involved children under 5 years of age, with an average age of 4.43 years. Males accounted for 53.5% of admissions. The highest admission rates were recorded in May and December. Chronic pathologies accounted for 6.5% of cases, 50% of which were related to sickle-cell anaemia. The average consultation time was 4 days, with 63.4% of patients consulting within the first 3 days of their illness. The main reasons for consultation were fever (62.4%), physical asthenia (25.1%), vomiting (23.3%), cough (14.7%) and diarrhoea (12.1%). The most common diagnoses were malaria (61.1%), anaemia (28%), gastroenteritis (12.7%), septicæmia (11.4%) and urinary tract infections (10.3%). The treatments prescribed mainly included antibiotic therapy (64.4%), antimalarials (57.7%), antipyretics (52.5%), infusions (43.9%) and blood transfusions (34.2%). The average length of hospital stay was 5 ± 4 days, with 42.3% of patients staying less than 4 days. The mortality rate was 8.1%, and 9.3% of patients were discharged against medical advice.

In conclusion, paediatric morbidity in the DRC remains dominated by communicable diseases such as malaria and gastroenteritis despite the global epidemiological transition. Developing a national epidemiological bulletin and training focused on the common pathologies identified could change the profile of paediatric morbidity and improve the quality of paediatric care in the country.

Introduction

Morbidity is a key public health indicator. It measures the number of people affected by disease, disability, handicap or dependency in a given population [1]. It reflects the primary diseases and causes of hospitalisation and accurately assesses health needs. Knowledge of morbidity significantly contributes to the planning and evaluation of health services while also providing information on a country's level of socio-economic development [2-4].

On a global scale, morbidity is changing due to the epidemiological transition, marked by a reduction in communicable diseases and an increase in non-communicable diseases [5-7]. Children, in particular, are not spared from this dynamic [6-8].

Analysis of paediatric hospital morbidity plays a key role. It enables us to monitor changes in children's health priorities and to identify the significant problems requiring greater attention [7]. This exercise is facilitated by disease registers and digitised health information systems [9,10]. However, these surveillance systems are lacking in many developing countries, particularly in paediatric health [7].

The lack of up-to-date data limits the development of appropriate strategies for children's hospital care. Regularly updating morbidity profiles makes it possible to identify priority problems and revise training programmes for healthcare staff to guarantee appropriate, high-quality care.

This study aims to describe the profile of paediatric hospital morbidity in the Democratic Republic of Congo to provide up-to-date information for improving paediatric health policies.

Environment, Patients and Methods

1. Environment

This study was carried out in five referral hospitals in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC). These health facilities were selected for their essential role in the provision of paediatric care, their geographical distribution, which provided a map of morbidity across different regions of the country, and the variety of populations they serve. The health facilities concerned are:

- Cliniques Universitaires de Lubumbashi: Located in Lubumbashi, the capital of Haut-Katanga province, these clinics are affiliated with the University of Lubumbashi. They are the second largest hospital centre in the city and in the south of the country, after the Jason Sendwe Hospital. They serve a predominantly urban population.

- Hôpital Général de Référence de Kinshasa (ex-Mama Yemo): Located in the city of Kinshasa, in the west of the country, this is the country's largest public-sector healthcare facility. It offers comprehensive healthcare, including specialist paediatric care, to a predominantly urban population.

- Kimbanseke Kimbanguiste Hospital: Also located in Kinshasa, in the commune of Kimbanseke, this hospital is run by the Kimbanguiste Church. It plays an important role in providing health services to the local population, most of whom live in urban and rural areas.

- Hôpital Général de Référence de Makiso: Located in Kisangani, in the northern province of Tshopo, this hospital serves as the main referral centre for the region, offering a full range of medical services, including specialist paediatric care.

- Kindu General Referral Hospital: Located in Kindu, in the province of Maniema, in the centre-east

of the DRC, this facility is the main healthcare provider in the region, offering essential and specialist medical services to an urban-rural population.

2. Patients

The data collected concerned all admissions to paediatric wards in the hospitals selected for the study, thus constituting an exhaustive sample. The patients included in the study ranged in age from 1 month to 20 years. Of the 2,483 cases registered during the study period, 2,170 were deemed suitable for use. Neonates and children admitted for severe acute malnutrition were excluded from the study.

3. Methods

3.1. Type and period

This study is a cross-sectional, retrospective, multicentre analysis of paediatric admissions recorded between 2019 and 2021 in the selected health facilities.

3.2. Variables of study

The variables analysed are grouped into three categories:

- Socio-demographic variables: age and gender
- Anamnestic variables: month of admission, presence of chronic diseases (known morbidity), transfusion history, the reason for consultation (symptom presented) and consultation delay (time elapsed since the onset of symptoms).
- Diagnostic and therapeutic variables: presumptive diagnosis (suspected morbidity),

treatment prescribed, length of stay, discharge arrangements.

3.3. Data collection and processing

Data were collected using a form developed by the Disease Prevention and Control Unit of Kindu University via the KoboCollect application.

Statistical processing of the data was carried out using SPSS version 25 and Microsoft Excel version 2017.

3.4. Data analysis

The statistical analyses mainly involved determining proportions and measures of trend, in particular means and standard deviations, in order to describe the characteristics of the population studied.

4. Ethical considerations

This study received ethical approval from the Faculty of Medicine at Kindu University. The administrations of the participating health facilities approved data collection. Data processing was carried out with strict respect for the anonymity of participants, following the ethical and regulatory standards in force in the Democratic Republic of Congo.

Results

1. Demographic characteristics of patients

A demographic analysis of the 2,170 paediatric admissions reveals a predominance of young children, particularly those aged under 5, who account for 70% of admissions. The average age of children admitted was 4.43 years. Males were the most represented at 53.5% (Table 1).

Table 1: Breakdown of Admissions by Age and Sex

Variables	Number (n=2170)	Percentage	Statistics
Age			Mean = 4.43 years Median = 3 years Mode= 2 years Minimum = 1 month Maximum = 20 years
1 to 59 months	1513	69.7	
1 to 5 months	271	12.5	
6 to 11 months	366	16.9	
12 to 23 months	361	16.6	
24 to 35 months	242	11.2	
36 to 47 months	142	6.5	
48 to 59 months	131	6.0	
5 to 10 years	401	18.5	
11 to 15 years old	221	10.2	
16 to 20 years old	35	1.6	
Sex			
Female	1009	46.5	
Male	1161	53.5	

2. Anamnestic characteristics of patients

Analysis of monthly pediatric admissions shows a relatively homogeneous distribution throughout the year, with notable peaks in May and December (Table II). Monthly admissions analysis over the study's three years reveals a consistent increase in December admissions across all collection sites. A notable peak in May admissions was also observed across all sites, particularly in 2020 (Figure 1).

Of the 6.5% of children with a history of illness, sickle cell disease was the most common, followed by malnutrition and bronchial asthma (Table II). Here, the malnutrition in question is an old episode already being treated and cured.

Regarding transfusion history, 15% of children had already received a blood transfusion. The average consultation time was 4 days, with 63.4% of children

consulting within 3 days of the onset of the first symptoms of the disease (Table 2).

Table 2: Distribution of Admissions According to the Month of Admission, Morbidity, Existence of Transfusion History and Consultation Time

Variables	Number (n=2170)	Percentage	Statistics
Month of admission			
January	191	8.8	
February	127	5.9	
March	156	7.2	
April	187	8.6	
May	278	12.8	
June	157	7.2	
July	171	7.9	
August	197	9.1	
September	165	7.6	
October	171	7.9	
November	114	5.3	
December	256	11.8	
Known morbidity			
None	2029	93.50	
Sickle cell disease	74	3.41	
Malnutrition	35	1.61	
Bronchial asthma	16	0.74	
HIV	8	0.37	
Tuberculosis	6	0.28	
Diabetes mellitus	5	0.23	
Congenital heart disease	1	0.05	
Epilepsy	1	0.05	
Transfusion history			
Absent	1843	84.9	
Present	327	15.1	
Consultation delay (days)			
≤ 3	1376	63.4	Mean=4 days
> 3	794	36.6	

Figure 1: Annual Evolution of Admissions by Month

3. Morbidity

The five main reasons for consultation recorded are fever (62.4%), physical asthenia (25.1%), vomiting (23.3%), cough (14.7%) and diarrhoea (12.1%).

The main diagnostic hypotheses mentioned in admitted children were malaria (61.1%), anaemia (28%), gastroenteritis (12.7%), septicemia (11.4%) and urinary tract infection (10.3%). These data are illustrated respectively in Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2: Distribution of Admissions According to Reasons for Consultation

Figure 3: Distribution of Admissions According to Diagnostic Hypothesis at Admission

4. Therapeutic and evolutionary modalities
 The average length of hospitalisation was 5±4 days, with 42.3% of admissions lasting less than 4 days. Regarding the discharge modality, it is observed that 9.3% of cases were discharged against medical advice and 8.1% of deaths (Table 3).

The primary therapeutic interventions administered to hospitalised children included antibiotics (64.4%), antimalarials (57.7%), antipyretics (52.5%), intravenous infusions (43.9%), and blood transfusions (34.2%). These are presented in Figure 4.

Table 3: Distribution of Admissions According to the Treatment Prescribed, the Duration of Doctor Stay and the Method of Discharge

Variables	Number (n=2170)	Percentage	Statistics
Length of stay (days)			
≤ 3	917	42.3	Average = 5 days Standard deviation = 4
4 – 7	844	38.9	
> 7	409	18.8	
Exit modality			
Improvement	1750	80.6	
Death	175	8.1	
DAMA	202	9.3	
Transfer	43	2.0	

Note: DAMA= discharge against medical advice

Figure 4: Distribution of Admissions According to the Treatment Prescribed on Admission

Discussion

1. Demographic characteristics of patients

Age

Children under 5 years of age represent 70% of admissions in our series, with a notable predominance of the age group of 6 to 23 months (33.5%). The average age of the children admitted was 4.43 years, with 2 and 3 years, respectively, as mode and median. Our finding corroborates that of many authors [7,9,11,12]. It differs from the result obtained by Diallo, who stated that the age group of 10 to 15 years was the most represented among admissions [13]. His finding was justified by the predominance of patients in this age group during consultations [13]. However, the findings in our series can be explained by the multifactorial vulnerability of children under 5 years [14,15]. Encouraging studies on the description of morbidity in this age group is essential.

Gender

The male sex is the most represented. This is consistent with the observations of many authors [8,9,11-13]. The predominance of the male sex among hospitalised children can be justified by the increased genetic predisposition of the XY genotype to morbid phenomena and particularly to infections [16].

2. Anamnestic characteristics of patients

Month of admission

The months of May and December recorded the highest number of admissions. A steady increase in admissions in December was observed at all sites over the three years of the study. Previous studies indicate that pediatric morbidity is influenced by seasons [17]. In tropical settings, the hot and rainy seasons and the transition from the rainy to the cold and dry seasons have been shown to correspond to periods of high hospitalisation [12,18-20]. In the DRC, the first period

includes the month of December, and the second is the month of May. These observations suggest the need for a thorough analysis of pediatric morbidity based on monthly and seasonal variations in order to adequately plan human and material resource needs.

Known morbidity

Only 6.5% of cases reported chronic pathology, and half were sickle cell disease cases. Previous studies report that the prevalence of chronic diseases in children varies between 10% and 30%, with an increasing trend [21,22]. The observation made in our series reveals an under-reporting of chronic diseases compared to the estimates of their prevalence in the pediatric population [23-30]. This can be explained by many factors such as (i) the limited accessibility of many children to the positive diagnosis of their morbid conditions, (ii) the non-use of the health card, (iii) the non-existence of chronic disease registries at both local hospital and national levels and (iv) a low active search for common morbid history in each setting. It is crucial to implement active hospital search for common chronic diseases in each setting and ensure that this information is properly documented.

Consultation delay

The average consultation time in our series is 4 days. Many studies conducted in African settings, notably by Bah, Doumbia, Kasongo, and Diallo, have found an approximate average of our series, but they have considered that the consultation time was long [12,13,31,32]. The consultation time can be correlated with the origin of the patients and the positioning of the receiving health facility on the pyramid of the health care system. The ideal remains a short consultation time to prevent the risk of disabling and/or fatal complications. It is up to the national healthcare system to set up a circuit that shortens the consultation time for children and defines the ideal time for each level of the healthcare pyramid.

3. Morbidity

Reason for consultation

The five most reported reasons for consultation in our series are fever (62.4%), physical asthenia (25.1%), vomiting (23.3%), cough (14.6%) and diarrhoea (12.1%). In Diallo's series (13), the main reasons for consultation were fever (96.2%), followed by seizures (50.9%), vomiting (41.5%), diarrhoea (37.1%), cough (31.6%) and physical asthenia (19.8%). Fever remains the most common reason for pediatric consultation, and this has been reported in several studies [13,31,32]. In-service training should aim to strengthen the capacities of pediatric care providers on the practical conduct to be adopted in the face of these main reasons for consultation.

Diagnosis on admission

Figure 3 shows that malaria (61.1%), anaemia (28%), gastroenteritis (12.7%), septicemia (11.4%) and urinary

tract infection (10.3%) are the five main diagnostic hypotheses mentioned in admitted children (Figure 2). Our results are similar to those found in other studies conducted in tropical settings [9,11-13,32]. Suspected morbidity remains invariable despite the epidemiological transition. On the other hand, Mhamdi [7] found that in Tunisia, there had already been a change in the profile of pediatric hospital morbidity. This change would be related to the epidemiological transition and the country's socio-economic progress. The observation made in our study can be explained by (i) the lack of contextualisation of the health information reporting system, (ii) the low use of complementary examinations and (iii) the punctual nature of general morbidity studies in children. The establishment of a national pediatric epidemiological bulletin can contribute to aligning data with trends in the epidemiological transition.

4. Therapeutic and evolutionary modalities

Prescribed treatment

The five main therapeutic measures prescribed for admitted children are antibiotic therapy (64.42%), antimalarials (57.70%), antipyretics (52.49%), infusions (43.87%) and blood transfusion (34.24%). The Zoghliami study in Tunisia found that antibiotic therapy was the most common treatment for children, with 34.3% [9]. A study will need to be conducted to assess the rationality of these therapeutic measures for children who have benefited from them.

Length of stay

The mean length of stay was 5±4 days, with 42.3% of admissions lasting less than 4 days. The mean length of hospital stay observed in our series is close to that found in the series of Zoghliami, Nsagha, Bah, Diallo and Doumbia [9,11-13,31]. It is essential to analyse the mean length of stay for each morbid condition that resulted in the hospitalisation of children.

Exit mode

Mortality among the cases collected in the study is 8.1%. It corroborates those reported by Bah and Diallo [12,13]. The best interpretation of this mortality is its specific study, particularly according to the month of admission, sex, age, consultation time and admission diagnosis.

Our results show that 9.3% of cases were discharged against medical advice. Our results are similar to those found by Mabilia in Brazzaville, where the proportion of discharges without and against medical advice represented 10.7% [33]. On the other hand, the proportion found in our series is higher than that found by other authors, and it varied from 1.3% to 4.29% [9,12,34,35]. Discharge without or against medical advice, commonly called "escape", is a discharge from the hospital without the knowledge of health personnel. It is a real problem in the administration of health care because it causes an increase in

readmission rates [33,35]. The scarcity of epidemiological data on this topic at the national level highlights the interest in its further study to circumscribe the factors justifying its high proportion in pediatric care settings.

5. Limit of the study

This study, conducted during the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic, took place in the context of global disruption of health systems. This potentially impacted the evolution of morbidity. Diagnostic hypotheses were based mainly on clinical and anamnestic assessments in the frequent absence of paraclinical confirmations, which could limit diagnostic accuracy. Despite these constraints, the data collected provide relevant information on pediatric morbidity in the Democratic Republic of Congo.

Conclusion

Suspected morbidity remains very invariable in pediatric care settings in the DRC despite the epidemiological transition observed worldwide. In pediatric hospital settings, it is dominated by children under 5 years of age. Establishing a national pediatric epidemiological bulletin will contribute to aligning data with trends in the epidemiological transition and thus improve the quality of pediatric care. Training in pediatric care should focus on the major facts noted in this study.

References

- [1] Raimondeau J. Chapitre 1. La santé publique, concepts et définitions de base. In: Santé publique. Rennes, France: Presses de l'EHESP; 2021:19-37.
- [2] World Health Organization. Statistiques sanitaires mondiales 2009. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2009.
- [3] Gaimard M. Santé, morbidité et mortalité des populations en développement. *Mondes en développement*. 2008;36(142):23-38. doi:10.3917/med.142.0023.
- [4] Aké-Assi MH, Eboua F, Koffi H, Adonis-Koffy L, Timité-Konan M. Evolution de la morbidité et de la mortalité dans le service de pédiatrie médicale du CHU de Yopougon de 1999 à 2003. *Rev Int Sc Méd*. 2009;11(1):7-12.
- [5] Paka E. Profil de la Transition Sanitaire en République du Congo. *ESI Preprints*. 2024;32:626-626.
- [6] Vallin J, Meslé F. De la transition épidémiologique à la transition sanitaire: L'improbable convergence générale. In: Caselli G, Vallin J, Wunsch G, eds. *Démographie: Analyse et synthèse, Volume VI: Mortalité et Santé*. Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium: Presses Universitaires de Louvain; 2003:257-290.
- [7] El Mhamdi S, Herizi C, Sriha A, Bouanene I, Ben Salah A, Gaaliche S, et al. Profil et tendances de la morbidité hospitalière pédiatrique au niveau de la région de Monastir (Tunisie) pendant une décennie. *Rev Med Brux*. 2015;36(5):410-414.
- [8] Garenne M, Gakusi E, Lery A. La transition sanitaire en Afrique subsaharienne. *Actual Dossier Santé Publique*. 2000;30:26-30.
- [9] Zoghalmi C, Horrigue I, Khelil M, Nouira S, Chebil D, Jrad T, et al. Typologie de la morbidité diagnostiquée dans un service de pédiatrie d'un hôpital secondaire (Msaken, Sousse, Tunisie). *Tunis Med*. 2021;99(1):106-119.
- [10] Desai A, Starmer A. Process metrics and outcomes to inform quality improvement in pediatric hospital medicine. *Pediatr Clin North Am*. 2019;66(6):1245-1257. doi:10.1016/j.pcl.2019.08.010.
- [11] Nsagha DS, Kamga HLF, Verla VS, Assob JCN, Njunda AL, Mpei E, et al. La Morbidité au Service de Pédiatrie de L'hôpital Régionale de Nkongsamba au Cameroun entre 2007 et 2011. *Afr J Integr Health*. 2015;5(1):1-8.
- [12] Bah A. Morbidité et mortalité des enfants au service de pédiatrie de l'hôpital Nianankoro Fomba de Ségou. *Mali Santé Publique*. 2021;13(1):81-84.
- [13] Diallo FB, Condé I, Bangoura K, Lamine M. Morbidité et mortalité chez les enfants de 0 à 15 ans hospitalisés au service de pédiatrie de l'hôpital préfectoral de Dubréka. *Rev Int Sc Méd*. 2022;14(1):1-7.
- [14] Nations Unies. Communiqué AG/SHC/3921. 2008. Les causes profondes contribuant à la vulnérabilité des enfants restent à analyser. Available from: <https://www.un.org/press/fr/2008/AGSHC3921.doc.htm>
- [15] Bourillon A. *Pédiatrie pour le praticien*. 6th ed. Paris: Elsevier Masson; 2011.
- [16] Hodges GR, Perkins RL. Acute bacterial meningitis: an analysis of factors influencing prognosis. *Am J Med Sci*. 1975;270(3):427-440. doi:10.1097/0000441-197511000-00010.
- [17] Breschi M, Livi Bacci M. Saison et climat comme contraintes de la survie des enfants. L'expérience italienne au XIXe siècle. *Ann Demogr Hist*. 1986;(2):11-31. doi:10.3406/adh.1986.1490.
- [18] Camara B, Diouf S, Faye PM, Ba A, Ba M, Sow D, et al. Morbi-mortalité en milieu hospitalier pédiatrique dakarois (Sénégal). *Arch Pediatr*. 2005;12(12):1777-1782. doi:10.1016/j.arcped.2005.09.023.
- [19] Vaahtera M, Kulmala T, Maleta K, Cullinan T, Salin M-L, Ashorn P. Epidemiology and predictors of infant morbidity in rural Malawi. *Paediatr Perinat*

Epidemiol. 2000;14(4):363-371. doi:10.1046/j.1365-3016.2000.00289.x.

[20] Raobijaona H, Rahanitrandasana O, Razanamparany M. Évolution de la pathologie infantile à Antananarivo-Madagascar sur une période de 5 ans. *Méd Afr Noire*. 2000;47(10):421-425.

[21] Consolini DM. Children with chronic illnesses. In: *MSD Manual Professional Edition*. 2022. Available from:

<https://www.msdmanuals.com/professional/pediatrics/caring-for-ill-children-and-their-families/children-with-chronic-illnesses>

[22] Halfon N, Newacheck PW. Evolving notions of childhood chronic illness. *JAMA*. 2010;303(7):665-6. doi: 10.1001/jama.2010.130

[23] World Health Organization. Sick-cell disease: a strategy for the WHO African Region: report of the Regional Director. WHO Regional Office for Africa; 2010. Report No.: AFR/RC60/8. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/1727>

[24] World Health Organization. Obesity and overweight: key facts. 2024. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/obesity-and-overweight>

[25] James JM. Asthma facts. Asthma & Allergy Foundation of America. 2024. Available from: <https://aafa.org/asthma/asthma-facts/>

[26] UNAIDS. Global HIV & AIDS statistics — Fact sheet. Available from: <https://www.unaids.org/en/resources/fact-sheet>

[27] World Health Organization. Tuberculosis: key facts. 2024. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/tuberculosis>

[28] Stanescu DE, Lord K, Lipman TH. The epidemiology of type 1 diabetes in children. *Endocrinol Metab Clin North Am*. 2012;41(4):679-94. doi: 10.1016/j.ecl.2012.07.009

[29] van der Linde D, Konings EE, Slager MA, Witsenburg M, Helbing WA, Takkenberg JJ, et al. Birth prevalence of congenital heart disease worldwide: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2011;58(21):2241-7. doi: 10.1016/j.jacc.2011.08.025

[30] Biset G, Abebaw N, Gebeyehu NA, Estifanos N, Birrie E, Tegegne KD. Prevalence, incidence, and trends of epilepsy among children and adolescents in Africa: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Public Health*. 2024;24:771. doi: 10.1186/s12889-024-13755-6

[31] Doumbia AK, Togo B, Togo P, Traore F, Coulibaly O, Dembele A, et al. Morbidity and mortality among children aged 1 to 59 months hospitalized in the general pediatrics department of Gabriel Toure University Hospital from January to December 2013. *Rev Mal Infect Microbiol*. 2016;11(1):7-12.

[32] Aubin KNW, Kanteng G, Luboya NO, Wembonyama SO. Hospital epidemiology of pediatric medical emergencies in Lubumbashi: cases from general referral hospitals. *Rev Afr Med Sante Publique*. 2023;6-7:1-6.

[33] Mabilia-Babela JR, Nika ER, Ollandzobo LC, Samba Louaka C, Mouko A, Mbika Cardorelle A, et al. Discharges against medical advice in pediatrics at the University Hospital of Brazzaville (Congo). *Bull Soc Pathol Exot*. 2011;104(5):331-5. doi: 10.1007/s13149-011-0151-9

[34] Adama D, Coulibaly O, Cissé ME, Maïga B. Factors favoring discharges against medical advice and refusals of hospitalization in the pediatric emergency department of Gabriel Touré University Hospital. *Mali Santé Publique*. 2022;54-7:1-4.

[35] Ouédraogo S, Kam M, Yé D. Discharges without or against medical advice at CHUP-CDG of Ouagadougou and associated factors (Burkina Faso). *Burkina Med*. 2017;21(2):1-6.

